

SHARING IMAGINATION AND EMOTION THROUGH THE USE OF LIVELY INTERACTIVE PRODUCTS

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ABSTRACT

People using the same product may also share meaning and affect. Grounded in phenomenology in philosophy, cognitive semantics in cognitive science, and the psychology of emotion, this paper argues that lively interactive products, which feature dynamic images with reactivity and contingency, can evoke shared mental images and feelings via familiar sensorimotor experience in two states of interaction, namely continuous feedback (i.e., coupling of user input and system feedback) and extended change (i.e., system change while input pauses). The overall enduring interaction triggers imaginative conceptual blends in users at multiple cognitive levels. Meanwhile, emotions are elicited during different moments. Users thus echo similar imagined thoughts and feelings through the use. This paper introduces interpretive analysis for designers or researchers, showing how the model assists in analyzing inter-subjective user experiences and opens up possibilities for creating more socially resonating products.

KEYWORDS: *Embodied cognition; imagination; emotion; interaction design; sensorimotor experience.*

INTRODUCTION

Through product use people often experience subjectively in terms of the involved sensory perception and bodily action, the memory, meaning, and emotion provoked, and the aesthetics presented. Meanwhile, a good design is able to provide a coherent experience to its users. Users experiencing the same design, especially among those which enable sharing may also recall common memories and share similar thoughts and feelings. This kind of experience belongs to the category of evocation, which is one of the hedonic product attributes delineated by Marc Hassenzahl (2003). Hassenzahl differentiated from pragmatic dimensions of user experience (UX), the three hedonic attributes, namely stimulation (users' personal growth), identification (users' self-expression as compared with others), and evocation (users' memories). Regarding evocation, Hassenzahl's discussion focuses on the relationship between products and single users. In fact, evocation can be extended to include multiple users engaged in shared memories, mental images, and feelings. Hence, evocative experience demonstrates a way toward what Jodi Forlizzi, Katja Battarbee, and Ilpo Koskinen called 'co-experience', which means a group of users co-creating meaning and emotion through the use of a product (Battarbee & Koskinen, 2008; Forlizzi & Battarbee, 2004).

Compared with such pragmatic dimensions of UX as efficiency and usability, which have been well addressed in the tradition of Human-Computer Interaction (HCI) and have become scientifically 'measurable' by user-evaluation approaches, other attributes like meaning and affect are too abstract and subjective to be accessed. Hendrik N. J. Schifferstein and Paul Hekkert (2008) edited a comprehensive volume of articles revolving around diverse facets of subjective experience of products. They advocated empirical approaches to studying these subjective dimensions via people's self-reporting (Schifferstein & Hekkert, 2008, p.5). Hassenzahl and Noam Tractinsky (2006) also believe that there have been enough conceptual investigations of UX, and more empirical research is required to advance the theories. After their calls, empirical studies of UX have been extended to relatively abstract facets like pleasantness and engagement (Hassenzahl et al., 2010; O'Brien, 2010; Rozendaal & Schifferstein, 2010). Yet, when dealing with the evocation of shared memories, past or inferred experiences, imagery, and affect, it is still controversial to assess these solely empirically. I argue that in the design process user evaluation should come with designer interpretation, because the former is assessment of the current state and therefore might not inform insights for future possibilities. In contrast, the latter, while theoretically grounded, can generate promising ideas for discovering new opportunities.

Designerly interpretive analysis can be applied in analyzing existing design artifacts (which connects the past to the current) as well as developing new ones (which connects the current to the future). This paper thus offers an interpretive approach grounded in embodied cognition ideas of the topic of inter-subjective experiences of interactive products. It first introduces the idea of what I call ‘lively interactive products’, followed by underlying concepts including those from phenomenology, cognitive semantics, and the psychology of emotion, which relates the characteristics of lively interactive products, including reactivity and contingency, to people’s imagination and affect via sensory perception and motor action. Lastly, it illustrates the notion by an array of existing and developing design artifacts.

LIVELY INTERACTIVE PRODUCTS

Everyday products by convention afford (offer the possibility of) motor action to people. By affordances, we follow J. J. Gibson’s ecological approach (Gibson, 1977; Kannengiesser & Gero, 2011). For example, a bed affords the action of lying down. A task chair affords the act of sitting upright and concentrating on the desktop work. On the other hand, some cases can involve multiple users. A couch affords to several people the act of sitting at a reclined position and enjoying the television. The television is intended to simultaneously engage several people’s attention towards its media content. A user can press buttons, either on the set or on the remote control, to select a favorite channel and enjoy with his or her companions. Sometimes, one may ask another to adjust the speaker volume. The group then listens to the television’s instant and incremental feedback on the audio level, until someone says the level is good and the enjoyment continues. It may happen that the audio level later becomes apparently too loud, probably due to a commercial break, a particular voice over, or the antenna reception, and one may need to adjust the volume again. In this scenario, the television demonstrates a certain degree of liveliness. It is reactive to user input, but also contingent upon other factors during the period of delivery.

By liveliness, I mean an interactive product that affords continuous motor action and perception of enduring change to the user in two states. On occasions, the user may perform continuous motor input and simultaneously perceive incremental change presented by the product without practical time lag, that is, a continuous sensorimotor feedback loop between the user and the product (Figure 1). On the other, the user may just perceive the change continuing indefinitely without giving any input. The user is probably engaged in subtle motor action (e.g., moving the eyeballs, or coming closer to peep, etc.; i.e., perception involves a certain degree of motor action), but the action is not an input to the feedback loop. The loop is temporarily suspended (Figure 2), and the change becomes indefinite and contingent upon other factors. In short, a lively interactive product features both reactivity and contingency. The overall change demonstrates a kind of ‘enduring interaction’ (Chow, 2012; Chow & Harrell, 2011).

Figure 1 Continuous feedback loops between users and lively interactive objects feature reactivity.

Figure 2 Indefinite change with temporary suspension of motor input implies contingency.

The phenomenon of enduring interaction exists in the use of many everyday things. Consider baking coffee with companions using a French press. You pour water into the beaker continuously until the rising water level reaches the desired marker or someone suggests a stop. You and your friends then observe the changing color inside the container or the aroma arising from it, until someone expresses that it is time to press the filter and enjoy. You and your companions try to control and fine-tune the current states toward the desired results (e.g., appropriate amount, temperature, and concentration). One is continuously engaged in motor action (e.g., pouring water, and then the coffee) and sensory perception (e.g., observing the water level, and the coffee color). Other examples include the tandem-riding experience. Both front and rear riders actively engage in cycling the pedals but only the former can steer with the handlebar. Meanwhile, both of them are sensing the resultant speed and changing direction. Sometimes, one may want to pause cycling and let the bicycle run freely. During these relatively inactive moments, the riders still keep sensing the change in speed (contingent upon the slope of the road) and may resume action soon. These common examples show that enduring interaction takes place in the use of many everyday things. At reactive moments, we act to input and perceive the output continuously and simultaneously. During contingent moments, we just perceive how a situation continues to change indefinitely. If the use of an interactive product is reminiscent of an enduring interaction in people’s past events or memories, the product can invoke shared imagination and affect among them. The following section provides the theoretical underpinning of this argument.

THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

For interactive products to evoke imagination and affect, lively attributes including reactivity and contingency are crucial. At reactive moments, the product use entails cognitive coupling of sensory perception and motor action, triggering users' impulsive desires, automatic appraisals, and immediate conceptual blends. During contingent moments, the product continues to show changes, suggesting to users imagined narratives via metaphorical blends and eliciting their emotions via extended appraisals of an apparent reality.

Cognitive coupling of sensory perception and motor action

The coupling of sensory perception and motor action has been central to the seminal study of developmental psychology initiated by the philosopher and psychologist Jean Piaget. To Piaget, infancy or what he called 'sensorimotor stage' is foundational to the development of one's cognition via simple acts like sucking and looking (Thelen, 1995, p.73). The computer scientist Ben Shneiderman, drawing upon Piaget, coined the term 'direct manipulation' and influenced the design of graphical user interfaces (GUI). The idea specifies physical action (e.g., the drag-and-drop mouse action) and visible feedback (e.g., change of appearance when an item is selected), bringing human-computer activity back to the level of early child development, which is easy to use and learn (Shneiderman, 2003 [1983]). Lately, S. A. G. Wensveen, J. P. Djajadiningrat, and C. J. Overbeeke have proposed a vigorous framework of coupling of action and feedback (Wensveen, Djajadiningrat, & Overbeeke, 2004). It introduces six aspects of coupling, including time, location, direction, dynamics (continuous or discrete motion), modality (sight, sound, or touch), and expression (related to users' states). Natural coupling should have no delay in time between action and feedback, both of which should take place at the same location and along the same direction. Continuity or discreteness of motion has to be consistent too. Among various aspects, I argue continuity in time and modality is more essential than location and direction for natural coupling in the use of lively interactive products.

In cognitive science, Esther Thelen has shown that infants start to develop various simple motor skills, such as reaching out or grasping, through continuous processes of 'integrated acts' of moving body parts and perceiving changes in environments. These changes vary continuously and infinitesimally, and a baby incrementally learns the force required to move muscles to an appropriate extent in a particular context (Thelen, 1995, p.90). Consider using a computer mouse to drag a file icon onto a folder icon in a GUI environment. A user keeps sliding the mouse while tracking the file icon moving on the display until it reaches the folder. This sensorimotor phenomenon is comparable to our physical experience of moving a piece of paper from the desk into a tray. When continuously moving our body parts, we need to simultaneously 'see' something being 'moved' from one location to another. Though the GUI

environment demands some kind of learning curve at first, a user can easily master the skill without noticing details of his or her action after some repetitions. This shows that with continuous feedback loops our bodies have the power to 'cognitively naturalize' a coupling even though the action and feedback mismatch in location and direction. This phenomenon is further explained in the next section.

Conceptual blends, material anchors, and material-based imagination

Lively interactive products entail coupling of action and perception, which readily invokes imagination in users. At reactive moments, the sensorimotor feedback loop, augmented with the dynamic change presented by the product, is usually reminiscent of one's past experiences. For example, PEGA D&E's Pumplight is a balloon-shaped table lamp (<http://www.pegadesign.com/en/portfolio-pumplight.html>), which has a pump (like those usually found in blood pressure meters) in place of the common switch. A user can inflate the balloon using the pump. When the balloon gets bigger, the light becomes brighter. The analogy in sensorimotor phenomenon readily and immediately provokes an imagined concept of 'pumping' energy into the lamp, that is, a blended image in users. During contingent moments, extended change without user input brings a set of related knowledge (in cognitive science's terms, 'frames') to the user's mind, yielding more elaborate imagination. For instance, TH Design's Tio is an intriguing eco-friendly light switch that shows changing color after the light is on (<http://timholley.de/2010/08/10/tio/>). It gradually turns from green to orange and then red in an eight-hour period, aiming to remind users of energy conservation. The changing color, together with emoticon-like facial expressions, invokes the 'tolerance' frame in users, suggesting an imaginative narrative of someone feeling annoyed with the light being on for too long. This is what Kenny K. N. Chow and D. Fox Harrell call 'material-based imagination' (Chow & Harrell, 2009; Chow & Harrell, 2012), grounded in theories of conceptual blends and material anchors, both from cognitive science.

Imagination (i.e., mental imagery) based on material images can take place at the automatic, perceptual level. Arguments suggesting a close relationship between mental images and perception include those of Ludwig Wittgenstein as described by Mitchell (1986), Arnheim (1969), Stafford (2007), and Johnson (2008). Once viewers perceive a material artifact as associated with some meaning (e.g., a clock face), the perceived image becomes a mental image (i.e., one can 'see' the displayed time even with eyes closed). Edwin Hutchins's concept of material anchors (2005) reciprocally theorizes the distribution of meaning (e.g., the time) onto physical structures (e.g., the clock face with the hands). Material anchors are structures or patterns that 'hold' crucial information in place for mental manipulation. In the case of an analog stopwatch, the position of the stopwatch's minute hand and the target time marking on its face form a circular sector that, when considered relative to a complete circle, informs the

user of the time left. Such a material image in the physical world can carry information for direct input to cognitive processes like conceptual blending.

Building upon the earlier concepts of mental spaces (Fauconnier, 1985) and conceptual metaphors (Lakoff & Johnson, 2003), Gilles Fauconnier and Mark Turner (2002) argue that conceptual blending is a basic mental operation that generates new meanings by integrating concepts, and forming emergent networks. Blending is pervasive in common sense meaning making, as well as in other creative feats like rhetoric, gameplay, and even in interface design (Fauconnier, 2001, p.279). Some blends can be so commonly exercised in everyday life that they become automatic and unnoticed. Fauconnier has cited the computer interface phenomenon as an example of this kind of immediate blend (pp. 264-65). For instance, a user dragging a window on a computer desktop slides the mouse on a real horizontal desk. Meanwhile, the user's eyes track the vertically-oriented movement of the graphics on the screen. There are a set of mappings between the physical space and the screen space, including from the mouse to the window, from the mouse click to the act of 'picking-up' the window, from forward to up, from backward to down, and so on. Most users, however, are unaware of the blend. They just feel that they are directly manipulating the window. This action-perception coupling seems to violate at least two aspects of Wensveen, et al. (2004)'s natural coupling, namely unified location and direction, but it becomes second nature to many computer users of today. This is indeed the power of conceptual blends enabled by interactive systems.

Chow and Harrell extend the above ideas to argue that interactive dynamic images (offered by lively interactive systems) can act as elastic material anchors for imaginative conceptual blends (Chow & Harrell, 2013). These images hold distilled dynamic information (like Pumplight's varied balloon size), and mobilize continuous sensorimotor feedback loops, provoking at reactive moments immediate imaginative blends that bridge the gaps in location or direction. During contingent moments, the images continue to change without user input (like Tio's changing color and emoticon). The perception of change usually gives users a concept of time. As the philosopher and psychologist William James puts it, 'awareness of change is [...] the condition on which our perception of time's flow depends' (1890, p.620). Psychologist J. J. Gibson also said that 'external stimuli [...] provide a flow of change, and it is this we perceive rather than a flow of time as such' (Gibson, 1975, p.299). Perception of change brings a set of concepts about time, including order, duration, beginning, and end. These temporal elements, together with the information held by the images, constitute the essence of an experience, or a narrative. Dewey has distinguished 'an experience' from 'experience'. The former is singular, 'having its own beginning and end' (Dewey, 1980, pp.35-36). Hence, an experience is comparable to a narrative. A sensorimotor experience of change readily provokes higher levels of imaginative blends in the form of narrative, which Chow and Harrell call metaphorical blends. Illustrative examples will follow in later sections.

Desire, appraisal, and the laws of emotion

Lively interactive products allow users to perform continuous motor action as input and to perceive enduring change. To really engage users in the sensorimotor phenomena, two components pertaining to affect are required. They are desire and appraisal.

Motor action and desire

From the phenomenologist point of view, continuous motor action or bodily motion embodies one's intention, desire, and so emotion. The continuity in time or motion is the key. Maurice Merleau-Ponty believes that through repeated practice our body can 'absorb' motor knowledge from the environment we inhabit and turn it into situated motor habits (Merleau-Ponty, 1962, pp.146-147). He called this the 'intentional arc', which is the 'power of laying out a past in order to move toward a future' (Merleau-Ponty, 1962, pp.135-136). The intentional arc exists in both space and time and works beneath the level of reflective thought. In other words, bodily motion embodies one's pre-reflective intention toward a desirable future state. Some thinkers have further argued that pre-reflective bodily motion is closely tied to one's emotion. To Roberta De Monticelli, emotions are 'vectors of (impulsive) action and of immediate action' (Monticelli, 2006, p.74). Michelle Maiese points out that emotion is based on one's impulsive, spontaneous, and pre-reflective intention to move the body self-expressively (Maiese, 2011, pp.62-63). This impulse is our first-order desire of 'wanting or not wanting things to be a certain way'. For instance, one feeling irritated about a radio commercial immediately turns the volume control knob anti-clockwise before any reflective thought. This is because the continuous nature of the knob fits the intentional arc. After repeated engagement one acquires the habit of turning the knob clockwise (or anti-clockwise) toward something desirable (or away from the undesirable). When one feels a need or want, the body spontaneously performs the corresponding movements that constitute embodiment of the desire. Hence, a lively interactive system affording continuous motor input with instant feedback tends to encourage users to act out their desires, and repeated engagement turns their actions into motor habits to express affective preferences. It follows that a radio receiver equipped with the variable volume control knob is more inviting to users' emotional impulses than one with only the toggle switch. The discrete nature of the latter hinders the habituation of affective motor action.

Perceivable change and appraisal

Lively interactive products feature perceivable enduring change. During both reactive and contingent moments, users assess the current state against the desired through perception. In addition to desire, assessment, or appraisal constitutes the core of our affect. To represent the raw feelings that exist within us, James A. Russell (2003) proposes what he calls 'core affect', a matrix of two dimensions, namely pleasantness and arousal. Pleasantness is 'an assessment of one's current condition', whereas arousal is 'one's sense of mobilization and

energy'. Russell believes that all moods and emotions can be reduced to a blend of the two dimensions, and this 'core affect is a continuous assessment of one's current state'. More importantly, this kind of assessment is often done via perception. As De Monticelli writes, 'feeling is essentially the perception of values' of things, and it can be positive or negative (Monticelli, 2006, pp.65-66). The alignment of Russell's and De Monticelli's views suggests that continuous assessment via perception constitutes our raw feelings. Another technical term for assessment is 'appraisal'. Paul Ekman has described appraisal of a current event as one of the characteristics of emotion (Ekman, 1992; 1994). He points out that the appraisal mechanism can operate automatically at the primary level or sometimes take place more reflectively at higher cognitive levels. The two mechanisms, namely *automatic* and *extended*, suggest appraisals of the enduring changes of interactive products during reactive and contingent moments respectively. Hence, at reactive moments impulsive desire and automatic appraisal join to result in affect. At contingent moments, extended appraisal may take place..

The laws of emotion

Lastly, Nico H. Frijda's two particular laws of emotion (1988), among others, also give support to the evocative power of lively interactive products. First, the law of change specifies that emotions are elicited by 'actual or expected changes in favorable or unfavorable conditions'. It is the change with respect to the current state that affects how a person feels. The enduring change presented by lively interactive products readily provokes users' emotional responses. Second, the law of apparent reality states that emotions are elicited by events that seem to be real. Images, pictures, photographs, sounds or voices, are taken to be more vivid and serious than words. As argued above, lively interactive products featuring dynamic images (or other sensory data) with enduring changes trigger imaginative blends, yielding immersive mental imagery. It follows from the above two laws that users will appraise the changes in the imagined situation as vividly real, and have emotions evoked.

INTERPRETIVE ANALYSES OF SHARING LIVELY INTERACTIVE PRODUCTS

Lively interactive products feature dynamic images with both reactivity and contingency, which are reminiscent of users' past or inferred experiences. This kind of embodied analogy provokes imagination in terms of conceptual blends at multiple levels and elicits emotion at different moments of interaction. This brings about the inter-subjective experience resonating among a group of shared users.

In summary, the analysis of inter-subjective experience includes the mappings from users' sensorimotor experiences to their cognitive and affective responses during the two states of interaction. The following two tables (Table 1 and 2) put together related aspects for considering the mappings:

SENSORIMOTOR EXPERIENCES	FOR IMAGINATIVE AND AFFECTIVE RESPONSES
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Users' motor input - Product's sensory feedback (including images, sounds, etc.) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Sensorimotor feedback loop anchoring an embodied concept - <i>Immediate</i> blend with past or inferred experiences outputting a new concept - <i>Impulsive</i> desire and <i>automatic</i> appraisal leading to emotional response

Table 1. Mapping experiences during reactive moments

SENSORIMOTOR EXPERIENCES	FOR IMAGINATIVE AND AFFECTIVE RESPONSES
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Product's overall enduring change 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Enduring change invoking a semantic frame - <i>Metaphorical</i> blend outputting imagined narrative like apparent reality - <i>Apparent reality</i> and <i>extended</i> appraisal leading to emotional response

Table 2: Mapping experiences during contingent moments

During reactive moments, the sensorimotor feedback loop has to be compared to certain common sensorimotor phenomenon in the user's everyday life, anchoring an embodied concept for *immediate blending*. The output of the blend will be an imagination. Meanwhile, the user's motor action has to be associated with an *impulsive desire*, and the object's instant feedback lets the user perform *automatic appraisal*, resulting in either a positive or negative affect (e.g., satisfaction, discontent, etc.). The affect also helps mobilize the sensorimotor feedback loop.

During contingent moments, the overall enduring change has to be in focus. It suggests a semantic frame with temporal and contingent elements, informing components to be mapped with those elaborated from the immediate blend and additionally the changes the user later perceives. These form the *metaphorical blend*, proposing an imaginative narrative or scenario. This material-based imagination has vivid images, and the user is engrossed in this *apparent reality* assessing the changing state. This *extended appraisal* results in further emotional responses.

To illustrate how the above model assists in understanding scenarios for people to share mental imagery and affect, analyses of sharing lively interactive products follow. They include a physical board game, a digital and tangible photo album, and a smart device for sharing umbrellas. The first one is an existing product, which represents the emergence of liveliness in today's design trends. The other two are artifacts designed and developed by students in School of Design, The Hong Kong

Polytechnic University, demonstrating how the proposed model can be applied in design processes.

The board game MELTDOWN

GEOLino MELTDOWN (<http://meltdown-game.com>) is a board game for a group of two to four players, aged five or above. Players prepare ice cubes with the given tray and then flip them onto the given spongy sheet to form the game board. The aim of the game is to move the polar bear-like tokens according to rolled dice before the ice melts beneath them (see Figure 3).

Figure 3 GEOLino MELTDOWN requires players to save the polar bears before the ice melts.

When players take turns to roll the dice, move the bears, and see them advancing, the game presents a dynamic image of pacing bears on the melting ice. To a player, this sensorimotor experience is reminiscent of playing common roll-and-move games like *The Game of Life*. The immediate blend is a family of bears running towards the larger center ice cube according to the dice. The blend allows the players to easily understand the gameplay, such as turn taking, moving steps, possible paths, and destination (that is also one of the common functions of conceptual blends in our everyday lives). Knowing the game goal, each player has an impulse to move a bear every time the dice are rolled. Seeing the dice and moving the bear,

one automatically appraises the result, which may be exciting or disappointing. The impulsive desire and automatic appraisal keep players in the sensorimotor feedback loop. Since the game is a cooperative game, all players should yield the similar blend, sharing the ups and downs during play.

The most intriguing mechanic of the game is that the ice cubes are melting enduringly. Even though it is not the turn for a particular player to move, one can still see the cubes going away. The meltdown time is contingent upon the room temperature, the ice condition, and other factors. This enduring change, together with the move-and-stop bears and the blue sponge, easily invokes the frame of global warming effects on the Arctic with temporal elements like time limit and order of meltdown. The metaphorical blend generates an imaginative narrative that resembles those documentary videos we saw on television shows in which a polar bear is hopelessly trapped in an isolated, small piece of floating ice and cannot get to the main iceberg nearby. It echoes the game's tagline, 'save the polar bears before the ice melts'. The imagined story, augmented with all the dynamic images, is so apparently real that it vividly immerses the whole group of players. They play and share the resulting feelings such as blessing, disappointment, or even regret. One might also wonder if the game outcomes shed any light on the real cases in the Arctic. Indeed, the game wishes to bring awareness of the topic to its target players.

Photo Turntable: a digital and tangible photo album

The second example is a new design by a graduate student (Yang Pu) from School of Design, The Hong Kong Polytechnic University. It is a tangible interactive system, providing new user experience in storing, organizing, and sharing digital photos. The concept combines traditional photo albums and vinyl music records into a special disc. To browse the photos, users just put the disc on the given turntable and spin it. The photos associated with the disc can be viewed either via a computer screen, or projected on the wall via the built-in projector, which facilitates sharing among a group in gathering (see Figure 4).

Figure 4. The Photo Turntable system includes physical product and software, allowing users to organize, view, and share photo collections in a tangible, nostalgic way.

When a user spins the disc, one can see the photos flipping consecutively. This continuous sensorimotor phenomenon is reminiscent of the past or inferred (after seeing others doing it) experience of turntable scratching or the use of the jog dial on professional videotape recorders, spinning clockwise to play forward and anticlockwise to rewind. The immediate blend results in a concept of photo record, which allows sequential access to photos with a rotary control. One's finger motion, including speed and direction, conveys the impulsive desire of viewing photos in succeeding or preceding order. Seeing the photos in sequence, one automatically appraises whether the previous or next photo is more interesting than the current one, and spins the disc anticlockwise or clockwise. The impulsive desire and automatic appraisal sustains the sensorimotor feedback loop.

Instead of looking for a target, the user may want to enjoy the album generally. If so, one can just press a button to let the turntable rev the disc, and then the photos will be shown in a slideshow. The show is contingent upon the particular disc content and the selected play mode. One can view the show with others in a gathering and share the pleasurable moments. The spinning disc with printed cover, the turntable, and the slideshow join to form an immersive relaxing atmosphere, evocative of listening to the gramophone with company in the old times. This invokes the corresponding frame. The metaphorical blend can be an imaginative narrative of friends coming to appreciate one's favorite albums. Based on friends' responses, one may appraise whether the current collection (of photos) is interesting to the 'audience'. All in all, viewing photos together and taking a glimpse of friends' exciting responses embody the happiness.

Umbrella Here: a smart device for sharing umbrellas

Umbrella Here (<http://www.umbrellahere.com/>) is another developing interactive smart device designed by a group of

students (Tommy Lau, Martin Tsang, Karen Wan, & Patience Lee) from School of Design, The Hong Kong Polytechnic University. The small device can sit on the desk indoors and connect to the owner's smartphone, receiving weather reports from the Internet and glowing differently with corresponding colors to remind him or her of bringing an umbrella. If attached, it makes the umbrella smart. It not only sends you notification of being left behind out of home, but more intriguingly, it glows at the top of the umbrella if it is put up in the rain. The light signals that the user is willing to share the umbrella with others. The device aims to mobilize mutual sharing between people (Figure 5).

When the user puts up the umbrella and walks in the rain, he or she can turn on the attached device light (through the smartphone) to invite people. If someone comes in and asks to share the umbrella, the user can turn the light off (or keep it on if the umbrella still has room!). The operation makes the user feel like they are doing a taxi driver's job. The analogy builds upon the sensorimotor experience of turning the light on and seeing someone search for a ride. Yet, this 'umbrella ride' is for sharing rather than hiring. The immediate blend outputs a new concept of inviting people to a free umbrella ride. To someone running across the street soaking-wet, the device light seems to be a lighthouse bringing hope in the heavy rain. To the 'umbrella driver', a 'passenger's' hopeful and thankful face is also very delightful.

When the user stays indoors, he or she may not actively engage with the device. It sits on the desk or table and enduringly glows in changing colors with the updated weather condition. The enduring and contingent (it's weather!) change does not just practically remind the user to bring an umbrella, but also emotionally signals that it is time to help others by giving a free ride again! It invokes the emergency service frame, which consists of elements like emergency call, person in need, urgency, safety, and so on. The device's glowing light is analogical to an

Figure 5 Umbrella Here can be attached to an umbrella to invite passers-by who get wet, or it can sit on a desk to show different colors based on an updated weather report.

emergency call, provoking images of someone getting wet in the street, waiting restlessly under a shelter, or even sliding on a slope. The metaphorical blend of the glowing light with the emergency call results in an imaginative narrative with the message: 'bring the umbrella and help others!'

Based on the proposed model summarized in Table 1 and 2, suggestions can be given on how to make the sensorimotor experience of putting up the inviting signal more embodied, and how to make the emergency signal more enduring for extended appraisal. The former includes more thoughts on gestural input, for example, shaking the smartphone up to raise the signal and shaking down to turn it off. The latter can be mapping different shades of color to the updated rain precipitation measurement. The user can then perceive the color darkening over a period of time and know the situation outdoors is getting worse. One would become increasingly worried about people outside.

CONCLUSION AND IMPLICATIONS

Lively interactive products feature dynamic images and enduring interaction, enabling imaginative conceptual blends at multiple levels, and eliciting affective responses at different moments. Hence, a group of users may share imagination and emotion through the product use. The interpretive analyses shown in this paper resonate with Forlizzi and Battarbee's suggestion for designers and researchers, 'mapping smaller experiences inside bigger ones' in order to 'understand relationships between small and large' (Forlizzi & Battarbee, 2004). Mapping sensorimotor experiences is important to understanding thought and feeling elicited in sharing interactive products. Meanwhile, it is well noted that the above interpretive analyses should be cross-referenced by empirical evaluation studies. Possible methods include retrospective self-reporting and prospective probing. Future empirical research is required to strengthen the proposition.

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